

Insight Digital Lending pathways
in Italy, Poland and Spain

(i)SDL Insight

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Report for Italy

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Abstract

The SDL Insight - Digital Lending pathways in Italy, Poland and Spain project, funded by Knowledge Rights 21 and coordinated by Deborah De Angelis, the Italian coordinator of KR21, aims to analyse digital lending (eLending), with a particular focus on Independent Secure Digital Lending (iSDL) in libraries across three European Union countries: Poland, Spain, and Italy. The project examines the factors and barriers that affect the full implementation of (i)SDL, serving as a starting point for developing strategies to overcome these challenges.

Participating in the project are the [DDA Law Firm](#), [CLAKP](#) (Copyright Law and Access to Knowledge Policies Group) of the IGSG (Institute of Legal Informatics and Judicial Systems)/CNR (National Research Council), the “Dario Nobili” Library of the Research Area of the National Research Council (CNR), the Library and Scientific Documentation Center of the CNR Research Area in Pisa for Italy, [Centrum Cyfrowe](#) in Poland, and [Fesabid](#) in Spain.

I. The Context

The project aims to gather information from Italian libraries concerning (independent) Secure Digital Lending (iSDL) — e-lending based on paper books digitised by libraries, with some protection measures adopted to prevent non-legitimate uses (for instance, measures to limit the lending time, to prevent downloading, etc., often called DRM - Digital Rights Management Systems).

(i)SDL is the digital counterpart to traditional lending for digitised works. A digitally secure environment allows libraries to lend out digitised works from their print collection under the same conditions as traditional lending (a book to a user for a limited time). In this way, libraries can fulfil their fundamental purpose of providing access to culture and knowledge by using existing technological possibilities and enabling, users to remotely access content that would otherwise be accessible only in person, among other things¹.

Italian legislation on copyright (Law No. 633 of April 22, 1941 (LdA)) provides a series of exceptions and limitations from which libraries benefit in carrying out their institutional function of sharing and providing access to knowledge for the community.

In particular, concerning the lending of digitised collections, it is noted how this service should shorten the distance between readers and works, allowing for better circulation and enjoyment of the latter. Digital library lending, an expression of the community's right of access to knowledge, is a key resource in support of measures to allow for example people

¹ E-lending in the (i)SDL model was developed as part of the report *eBooks and Secure Digital Lending in European Libraries* (<https://www.knowledgerights21.org/reports/ebook-sdl-report/>). In detail, e-lending based on the (i)SDL model is characterised by the following features: 1) Loans are made by strictly defined entities - establishments accessible to the public (e.g., libraries) that derive no direct or indirect economic or commercial advantage from their lending activity (requirement for a special case); 2) Lending covers the lending of a digital copy of a book; 3) Loans are made under the one copy - one user model; 4) Lending is carried out in a mimetic (i.e., allowing patrons to download electronic copies of books) or a quasi-mimetic fashion (i.e., allowing the use of electronic copies of books in streaming); 5) Lending is only for a limited period; 6) After the lending period has expired, the user cannot use the e-book; 7) A digital copy of a book must be obtained from a lawful source, but the library can make an electronic copy of a legally obtained copy of a paper book; e-lending under the (i)SDL model gives rise to the right to remuneration (PLR) in line with the Rental and Lending Directive; 8) there is no transfer of data, including personal data of library patrons, to publishers or other third parties.

with disabilities or those who cannot physically access libraries the opportunity to benefit from their services. This need has manifested itself in all its disruptiveness during the pandemic, and indeed has forced an acceleration in rethinking some of the limitations still imposed by legislation, which still operates as if literary works have a purely physical/analogous dimension.

The relevant Italian regulation does not provide exceptions and limitations to copyright specifically for (i)SDL; on the contrary, the existing regulations, far from being broadly formulated, refer exclusively to the work in its printed version.

Libraries, therefore, cannot rely on any explicit national regulations to lend digitised printed books, and consequently navigate in an uncertain environment.

In this context, the Judgment of the Court of Justice of the European Union of 10 November 2016, C-174/15 on e-lending by libraries in the EU is relevant. The Court ruled that digital lending can fall under the public lending exception in EU law, provided it follows a "one copy, one user" model, aligning with Directive 2006/115/EC. According to the order, for e-lending to be lawful, libraries must hold a legitimate digital copy. The Court did not address whether libraries can digitise their books under EU exceptions, though the Advocate General supported this possibility. Overall, traditional interpretations hinder widespread adoption of e-lending across the EU².

To enable libraries to implement the (i)SDL model, according to the study *e-Books and Secure Digital Lending in European Libraries: Comparative Analysis under National and International Law*³, two key rights need to be in place: (1) the right to digitise paper books and (2) the right to lend them, including via e-Lending.

Under current Italian Copyright law, the digitisation of paper books could potentially be based on Section 68(2), which authorises libraries, schools, public museums, and public archives to carry out photocopying of works available in their collections for their own services, provided there is no direct or indirect economic or commercial advantage. While this provision does not impose quantitative restrictions on the number of reproduced books, it is not technology-neutral, as it explicitly refers to "photocopying" rather than using the broader concept of "reproduction." Therefore, extending this exception to include digitisation would require a **dynamic interpretation of "photocopying" to encompass digital scanning**. However, such an interpretation is particularly challenging, given that under Italian law exceptions and limitations to copyright cannot be applied by analogy. For this reason, and in order to uphold the principle of legal certainty, **a legislative amendment would be necessary to explicitly authorise digitisation for (i)SDL purposes**.

As for e-lending, Section 69(1) could serve as a basis; however, this provision explicitly applies only to printed copies of works, making it difficult to interpret it in line with the CJEU VOB ruling on e-lending, which endorsed a "one copy, one user" model under certain conditions. Given that Italian law currently limits public lending rights (PLR) provisions to paper books, audiobooks, and audiovisual materials, applying them directly to digitised books is not straightforward.

² Gliściński, Konrad, Towards e-Lending by Libraries. Judgment of the Court of Justice of the European Union of 10 November 2016, C-174/15 (December 16, 2024). Available at <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5063346>; <https://ruj.uj.edu.pl/server/api/core/bitstreams/7d14abee-35c6-4dcf-86e0-902cc02a6da4/content>

³ Gliściński, K. (2025). e-BOOKS AND SECURE DIGITAL LENDING IN EUROPEAN LIBRARIES. Comparative Analysis under National and International Law. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10960187>

Nevertheless, as highlighted in the Centrum Cyfrowe report, **these limitations do not make (i)SDL impossible**. Rather, they indicate that while the legal basis may exist through dynamic interpretation aligned with EU principles, **clear legislative guidance and institutional capacity-building are needed to enable libraries to implement (i)SDL securely and confidently**.

This situation gives rise to the need to investigate the potential application of (i)SDL in Italy to assess whether libraries, in this context, can provide the services which they are intended to provide.

II. Survey objectives

The survey aims to investigate (i)SDL in Italy from the perspective of libraries to identify legal, technological, and infrastructure barriers, risk of opposition, and questions around human resources and financial burdens. An online questionnaire was sent to Italian libraries through a Google form to better understand relevant issues related to (i)SDL. The survey aimed to gather initial information on the topic to lay the groundwork for future initiatives.

III. The Questionnaire

A. Data and Methodology

A.1 Description of the questionnaire and the survey process.

From the outset, the survey was conceived to paint a picture of (i)SDL in the Italian library landscape.

The questionnaire was designed to collect initial data that could be useful for understanding the critical aspects of the implementation of (i)SDL in Italian libraries, and investigating the different types of barriers. Specifically, the intent is to outline a course of action to enable libraries to disseminate culture and knowledge in the digital environment.

This section describes the questionnaire's population (A.1.1.), structure (A.1.2.), and dissemination methods (A.1.3.).

A.1.1 Questionnaire recipients

The most authoritative directory of Italian libraries is the Anagrafe delle biblioteche italiane, managed by ICCU, the Istituto Centrale per il Catalogo Unico⁴. According to the Anagrafe, as at December 31st, 2024, there are 13.639 libraries in Italy⁵.

Libraries are distributed all over the 20 Italian regions, as illustrated in Figure 1. Lombardia (15%), Piemonte and Lazio (9%), Emilia Romagna, Campania and Veneto (8%) are the regions with the most libraries.

⁴ The Anagrafe of Italian libraries, available at <https://anagrafe.iccu.sbn.it/it/>

⁵ The Anagrafe's statistics are updated yearly, they can be accessed at <https://anagrafe.iccu.sbn.it/it/statistiche/statistiche-al-31-12-2024/>

Figure 1: Distribution of libraries per region. Source: ICCU statistics

According to the Anagrafe, Italian libraries are subdivided into 6 “functional types”: public (52,8%), special (24,1%), institutes for higher education, such as universities, music conservatories, etc. (9,6%), school (8%), libraries and institutes of conservation (5,3%) and national central (0%), as illustrated in Figure 2. The ICCU functional types are similar to the IFLA classification, but not perfectly overlapping.

Figure 2: Italian libraries grouped by “functional types”. Source: ICCU statistics

Since ICCU is the Italian authority for assigning ISIL codes, all libraries in the Anagrafe have their own unique ISIL identifier.

Since the target group of the questionnaire was the entirety of Italian libraries, we decided to use Anagrafe data, in particular email addresses, to reach all Italian libraries.

The data of the Anagrafe are issued under a CC0 license in the form of Open Data, updated daily, in CSV, XML and JSON format, and in turn compressed in ZIP format, and are grouped to form different datasets. Most libraries are described with a high level of detail, but

for some there are only identifying data and addresses. Moreover, some libraries do not update their data, so we decided to select only those libraries which had updated their data since 2020. In this way we obtained from the Anagrafe a set of 11 710 libraries. However, not all of them had associated email addresses.

It is worth adding that in 2024, Anagrafe data concerning of Italian Libraries was imported into Wikidata⁶ - itself an important task. We therefore checked if Wikidata contained more updated data with respect to our dataset, looking in particular for the email addresses that we needed in order to send the questionnaire.

Eventually, we obtained a final dataset of 10739 libraries having unique email addresses, to which we sent the link to the questionnaire. All of them have an ISIL code, which helped to detect possible duplicated answers, as well as allowing us to double-check characterisations of library type. For this reason, we decided to ask libraries to share their ISIL code in their responses .

A.1.2 Questionnaire Structure

The questionnaire was structured to reflect several elements that are essential for an optimal response outcome.

Given the very specific subject matter, it was deemed necessary to make the questionnaire easy to navigate, with the aim of encouraging participation.

The questionnaire is divided into eight sections: I. Library profile, II. Digital lending, III. Legal barriers, IV. Technological and infrastructure barriers, V. Risk of opposition, VI. Human resources, VII. Financial barriers, VIII. Others.

Several sections included the possibility to provide free-text comments.

The questionnaire was administered anonymously, and the information needed to identify the type of library for which one was responding and the role covered by the respondent was asked for.

The Italian partners of the project drafted the questionnaire questions, namely [DDA Law Firm](#), [CLAKP](#) (Copyright Law and Access to Knowledge Policies Group) of the IGSG (Institute of Legal Informatics and Judicial Systems)/CNR (National Research Council). The same questionnaire was then shared with foreign partners: [Centrum Cyfrowe](#) for Poland, and [Fesabid](#) for Spain. They provided interesting suggestions and valuable comments to define the final draft, which was further revised by Stephen Wyber of Knowledge Rights 21 and then translated into Italian, Polish and Spanish.

A.1.3 Questionnaire Distribution

A dedicated mailing list was populated with the 10739 email addresses to allow us to reach all our target libraries at the same time, and to send reminders easily.

The invitation email was sent on 5 February 2025 and the questionnaire remained available until 3 March 2025. Reminders were repeated on 19 and 25 February.

⁶ Rolleri, Davide, Importazione dell'Anagrafe delle biblioteche italiane in Wikidata, presented at Wikidata Days, Bologna, 8-9 November 2024. Available at https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Importazione_dell%E2%80%99Anagrafe_delle_Biblioteche_Italiane_in_Wikidata.pdf

Reminders have been sent to specialised libraries mailing lists too.

A.2 Number of answers

The data collection process generated a total of 449 completed questionnaires (number corresponding to about 4,18% of the invited guests).

Using the International Standard Identifier for Libraries and related organizations - ISIL - code⁷, it was found that four libraries had filled out the questionnaire more than once by different individuals.

Since the responses provided by the same libraries were dissimilar, we eliminated the responses of the aforementioned four libraries, reaching a total of **440 completed questionnaires (number corresponding to about 4,10% of the invited guests)** that are analyzed in this report.

A.2.1 Data cleaning and data integration

The next phase was devoted to data cleaning and data integration using, as an external source, the libraries dataset extracted from the Anagrafe.

All the 440 respondents declared the library's name and the correspondent ISIL code (this was Q1 of the questionnaire). The ISIL was actually not always entered correctly, so we had to clean some of these codes (for instance: we found codes missing one digit, or another "regional" code was declared instead). Eventually, matching the library name in the original source file extracted from the Anagrafe, we were able to obtain a set of 438 answers having the right ISIL code. Only 2 libraries still lacked the ISIL, however, since they have very generic names (Biblioteca europea and Biblioteca universitaria), it was not possible to retrieve and match them with their ISIL code.

Matching the ISIL codes with the rich data contained in the Anagrafe, it was possible to associate each library to an Italian region. All the 20 Italian regions are represented in the questionnaire. Lombardia (15%), Piemonte and Emilia Romagna (12%), Lazio (10%) were the most represented. The distribution of our respondents per region reflected the very similar distribution of Italian libraries per region (see Figure 1).

⁷ ISIL code was required as mandatory additional information in the first question of the questionnaire.

Data cleaning was necessary also for “Q3. What type of library are you answering for? Following IFLA’s typology (National, Academic, Public, School, Other)”. In fact, the option “Other” was chosen by 103 (24%) respondents, resulting in a long list of free text occurrences. So, we decided to match the IFLA types with the 2 data categories that came from the Anagrafe: the Functional type and the Administrative type. The ICCU functional types group libraries by their function, similarly to the IFLA classification (but with slight differences), while the Administrative type groups libraries by their parent institution, e.g. University, or Municipality, Religious institution, etc...). The ISIL code, again, helped us to merge our answers with the richer Anagrafe dataset. In this way, we were able to reduce the share of respondents assigned to the generic “Other” type to just 19%, by re-assigning some of them to Academic, Public and National types. We also reassigned some research, public and private libraries to the Academic type, according to the IFLA classification: an “Academic library is a library whose primary function is to cover the information needs of learning and research. This includes libraries of institutions of higher education and general research libraries.”

B. Results

B.1. Responses to Section I - THE PROFILE OF RESPONDENTS

The section dedicated to 'the profile of responding libraries' aimed to investigate the respondent’s role in the library, the type of library (following IFLA’s typology), the type and size of (physical and digital) collections, and if the library has a dedicated team to manage digital services or collections.

The data analysis will provide a detailed overview of the participating libraries.

Q2. What is your role in the library?

76% of respondents are Directors or Librarians (respectively, 39%, or 170, are Library Directors or have a directive/managerial role, and 37%, or 163, are Librarians), while 15%

(68) are Library Staff, 2% (10) are administrative employees, and the remaining 7% (29) have other roles in the library (such as: volunteer, intern, teacher, secretary, etc..).

Q3. What type of library are you answering for? Following IFLA's typology.

56% (248) of respondents are public libraries, 20% (89) are academic, 4% (16) are school libraries and 1% (4) are national libraries. The remaining 19% (83) fall in the other category, that was cleaned as described in Paragraph 2.1.

This distribution of our sample seems to reflect the distribution by type within our entire target population. Furthermore, we can observe that, in percentage terms, the academic libraries in our sample (89) represent 6.7% of the total number of academic libraries (1,312), which may suggest a greater sensitivity of academic libraries to the iSDL topic (especially when compared to the overall response rate of 4.10%).

Q3. Libraries by type

Q4. What types of collections does your library primarily hold?(Select all that apply)

This question allowed multiple answers. The vertical axis represents the number of libraries that selected each type of collection in their responses to Question 4. For example, 431 libraries (equal to 98%) reported holding monographs, while 258 (59%) hold serials, 203 (46%) multimedia, 140 (32%) archival materials, 103 (23%) e-only resources, 53 (12%) holds public domain or out-of-copyright materials and 38 (9%) other types of materials.

Q4. Collections owned by libraries

Q5. What is the size of your library's physical collection?

The majority of respondents (61,6 % (271)) declared that they possessed a large or a very large physical collection, while 36,1 % (159) of respondents declared a medium collection and only 2,3 % (10) possess a small physical collection.

Q5. Size of your library's physical collection

Q6. What is the size of your library's digital collection?

The majority of respondents 68,4 % (301) declared to possess a small digital collection, while 15,7 % (69) of respondents declared a medium collection and the other 16 % (70) a large or a very large digital collection.

Q6. Size of your library's digital collection

Q7. Does your library have a dedicated team to manage digital services or collections?

73% (320) of respondents said they do not have dedicated human resources to digital services or collections, while 25% (112) declare they have them and 2% (8) do not know.

If we analyse this response by library type, we see that 80% of public libraries reported not having dedicated staff, a percentage that drops to 49% for academic libraries. Conversely, 17% of public libraries and 51% of academic libraries do have dedicated staff.

Q7. Human resources dedicated to digital services

B.2. Responses to Section II - DIGITAL LENDING

The section dedicated to 'digital lending' aimed to investigate the current digital lending offerings of libraries, their practices for digitising physical works, the existence of user demand for (i)SDL models, the projected growth of this demand in the future, and finally, the perceived importance of offering an (i)SDL service for their library.

The data analysis will provide a detailed overview of the current state and prospects of digital lending within the context of the participating libraries.

Q8. Does your library provide an e-lending service?

Out of the 440 participating libraries, 62.05% (273 units) reported that their library does not offer an e-lending service, while 36.14% (159 units) stated that their institution provides such a service. Only 1.82% of respondents (8 units) were unable to provide information on the matter.

Q8. Does your library provide an e-lending service?

The analysis of the responses reveals a clear polarisation among the participating libraries.

Most responses highlight how, despite the increasing importance of digital resources, a significant portion of the libraries involved have not yet implemented such a service. This absence could reflect various dynamics, including budget limitations, lack of adequate technological infrastructure, strategic priorities oriented towards other services, or a perception of low demand from their users. Subsequent responses to the questionnaire shed more light on this question.

Conversely, a considerable 36.14% of the libraries involved state that they provide a digital lending service, indicating an awareness and commitment to integrating digital resources into the library's offerings, potentially meeting the needs of a wider and more diverse user base, including those who prefer or need to access materials remotely.

Finally, the minimal percentage of 1.82% who were unable to provide information on the matter could indicate a lack of specific awareness on the topic within the organisation or a phase of transition or evaluation of the service.

Q9. If you answer “yes” to the question above, please specify your library's current digital lending model.

Regarding the 159 positive responses to the previous question, 86.79% of the libraries (138 units) that stated they provide a digital lending service specify that it is a digital lending service for specific resources. Only 10.06% (16 units) provide a digital lending service for their entire collection.

Finally, 3.14% (5 units), while stating that they offer digital lending, do not indicate whether this service is provided only for specific resources or for the entire collection.

Q9. If you answer “yes” to the question above, please specify your library's current digital lending model

■ Digital lending for designated resources ■ Digital lending of the entire collection ■ I don't know

The majority approach suggests a cautious or selective strategy in digitisation and offering digital loans, likely focused on certain types of materials (such as ebooks, journal articles, or educational resources) or specific agreements with publishers and suppliers. This choice could be dictated by budget considerations, copyright restrictions, or an assessment of the specific demand for certain types of digital content.

Only a not insignificant minority offers a digital lending service for their entire collection. Although potentially more costly in terms of digitisation and rights management, this model demonstrates a broader commitment to digital access and a willingness to make the entire library collection available in digital format, where possible.

Finally, a small 3.14% do not specify the extent of the service (whether limited or extended to the entire collection). This lack of detail could be due to incompleteness in the response or a phase of defining or implementing the service.

Q10. Does your library digitise physical works and lend digital copies under (i)SDL?

Among 440 participating libraries, 93.18% (410 units) state that they do not digitize physical copies of works and therefore do not offer them for digital lending using the (i)SDL model. Only 3.86% (17 units) state that they digitize and lend such works digitally, according to the (i)SDL model. Finally, 2.95% (13 units) answer "Don't know".

Q10. Does your library digitise physical works and lend digital copies under (i)SDL?

The analysis of the responses reveals a picture of very limited implementation at present.

The overwhelming majority of participating libraries underscores how the adoption of (i)SDL is still low. This can be for multiple reasons, including issues related to copyright on digitisation, the technical and managerial complexity of (i)SDL implementation, the costs associated with digitisation and the technology platform, or a lack of strategic priority in this regard. All of these topics are explored further in this analysis.

Only a small percentage state that they digitise and offer physical works for digital lending by adopting the (i)SDL model, representing a vanguard in exploring innovative solutions to broaden access to their collections, potentially enhancing unique or hard-to-find works and reaching a wider audience, including those who cannot physically access the library.

Finally, those that answer "Don't know" express an uncertainty that could indicate a lack of specific knowledge of the (i)SDL model within the organisation, or a preliminary phase of evaluating its possible adoption.

Q11. If you answer "yes" to the question above, which of the following types of material do you lend under (i)SDL? (Select all that apply)

Among the 17 libraries that answer "yes" to the previous question, 16 then specify the type of material offered for digital lending using the (i)SDL model.

Within the types of material, out of a total of 26 selections, "Public domain works" prevail (the option was selected 11 times), followed by "In-copyright works which are out of commerce" and "In-copyright works which are on sale but only in paper format" (both select 4 times) and "In-copyright works which are on sale, also in electronic format" (select 3 times).

Under the "Other" category (select 4 times), the following types are indicated: historical archival documentation, local history, musical scores, and periodicals.

Q11. If you answer “yes” to the question above, which of the following types of material do you lend under (i)SDL?

The analysis of the responses (albeit already on a small sample size) highlights a clear prevalence of public domain works. This strategic choice appears logical, as such works do not have copyright restrictions, greatly simplifying digitisation and digital distribution.

The selection of "In-copyright works which are out of commerce" and "In-copyright works which are on sale but only in paper format" suggests an attempt to enhance and make accessible otherwise hard-to-find works, filling potential gaps in the commercial digital offering and responding to specific research or historical-cultural interest needs.

The "In-copyright works which are on sale, also in electronic format" category represents a less frequent choice. The use of (i)SDL for this type of material could be motivated by the desire to offer an alternative to traditional digital purchasing or to provide temporary access to requested texts, even with a commercial offering.

Finally, the "Other" category includes heterogeneous types of material, underscoring the potential versatility of the (i)SDL model in adapting to different types of content.

Q12. Is there/would there be a demand for (i)SDL services from your library’s users? Please specify the answer.

Among the 440 respondents, 37.95% (167 units) state that they do not currently perceive a demand for this type of service. In contrast, 17.50% (77 units) indicate a moderate demand,

and 27.05% (119 units) report a very little demand. Only a minority, represented by 4.32% (19 units), highlighted a high demand for (i)SDL, with an additional 13.18% (58 units) stating that they were unable to make an assessment.

Q12. Is there/would there be a demand for (i)SDL services from your library's users?

■ Yes, there is high demand
 ■ Yes, but the demand is moderate
 ■ Very little demand
 ■ No demand
 ■ I don't know

Libraries reporting a high demand for (i)SDL tend to be highly specialised institutions. This has been attributed both to the nature of their digital resources (unique materials or those difficult to find on general digital lending platforms, such as historical documents) and to the specificity of their users (particularly university students, including those studying remotely, who require flexible access to study materials). For these, (i)SDL may offer an incomparable way of meeting needs. The pandemic experience has also been cited as a factor contributing to the increased demand for (i)SDL. Furthermore, joining the MLOL (MediaLibraryOnLine) platform seems to have significantly increased the demand for (i)SDL for the libraries that are part of it.

Respondents observing a moderate demand for (i)SDL often link it to suboptimal communication of the digital lending service offered by the library itself, together with a lack of adequate equipment and staff specifically dedicated to this service. Some libraries operating in the humanities area have also specified that the move to increase the share of digital content in their collections proceeds more slowly due to a lower supply of digital content from publishers.

Libraries that record very little demand for (i)SDL indicate as determining factors the prevailing type of user (for example, an elderly population), insufficient communication of the digital lending service, the shortage of adequate human and financial resources, and the nature of the collections held, which may include out-of-print publications, ancient documents, photographs, and audio/video recordings still subject to copyright and, therefore, not easily digitised and distributed. In addition, some libraries have specified that the nature of some materials in their physical collections, such as ceramic works or paper scores, does not easily lend itself to digitisation and therefore to digital lending.

Finally, the lack of demand for (i)SDL is predominantly attributed to the type of user,

characterised by a low familiarity with digital technologies, as in the case of libraries mainly frequented by the elderly or children.

Q13. Do you foresee that this demand, in the coming years, will:

Out of a total of 440 responses, 34.09% (150 units) state that they foresee a marginal increase in the demand for (i)SDL in the future, and 30.91% (136 units) have no prediction. 18.18% (80 units) of the respondents indicate the demand is expected to remain stable, while for 0.68% (3 units) it should decrease, and for 16.14% (71 units) it should increase strongly.

Q13. Do you foresee that this demand, in the coming years, will:

■ Increase strongly ■ Increase marginally ■ Stay stable ■ Decline ■ Don't know

The analysis of the forecasts reveals cautious optimism, with half expecting a marginal or significant increase in the demand for (i)SDL. This trend suggests a general awareness of the potential of digital lending, but also a certain prudence in growth expectations, perhaps linked to current user dynamics or uncertainties about the large-scale adoption of the model.

Another significant proportion of respondents state that they do not have a defined forecast on the matter. This uncertainty could reflect a lack of specific historical data on (i)SDL, a difficulty in predicting the evolution of user habits, or the influence of external factors such as technological developments and editorial policies.

A considerable proportion anticipates that the demand for (i)SDL will remain stable, and this could be related to the specific characteristics of the current user base (for example, a prevalence of less digitally inclined age groups) or the perception that existing digital services (such as MLOL) are already sufficient to meet demand.

The decrease in demand could be linked to specific trends observed in their user base or a belief that other formats or modes of access to information will prevail.

Finally, a significant proportion is decidedly optimistic, predicting a strong increase in the demand for (i)SDL in the coming years. This perspective could be fueled by an expectation

of increasing user familiarity with digital technology, an awareness of the advantages of remote access, and a desire to enhance unique collections through digitisation.

Q14. In your opinion, how important is it for your library to offer a (i)SDL service? Please explain why _____

Of the 440 respondents, 56.36% (248 units) consider offering an (i)SDL service important but not essential. For 19.32% (85 units), the (i)SDL service is not important, while for 11.82% (52 units) it is essential. 12.50% (55 units) state that they do not know how to answer.

Q14. In your opinion, how important is it for your library to offer a (i)SDL service?

Essential Important but not essential Not important Don't know

Most libraries, considering (i)SDL important but not essential, recognise its potential advantages for both users and the institution itself. For users, the possibility of remote access to materials is highlighted, meeting work and study needs in an increasingly agile and mobile work environment, as well as those of users with disabilities.

For the institution (i)SDL is seen as an opportunity to expand their collection without physical space constraints, with consequent benefits in terms of premises management. However, this group of libraries also emphasises its non-essential nature, given the current low or absent demand from some specific user base (e.g., elderly, less inclined to use digital formats, children, or specialised users who prefer on-site consultation due to the nature of the materials) and to different factors such as preference for print, familiarity with other digital lending services (such as MLOL).

Furthermore, many libraries report preserving a unique and valuable heritage, often consisting of rare paper material, manuscripts, or archival documents, whose optimal use they believe occurs through direct physical consultation. Others highlight different investment priorities, especially those recently opened or with limited resources, which push them to focus on expanding services deemed more urgent and essential for their community.

A considerable number of participating libraries expressed, instead, a clear position of indifference regarding the offer of an (i)SDL service to their users. As with those suggesting (i)SDL was desirable but not essential, this response linked to the lack of interest or

familiarity with digital formats and technologies among users of the particular library, and their preference for the social and cultural experience offered by attending the library as a place. Another factor is membership in larger library systems (such as SBN Poles or provincial networks) that already give access to consolidated digital lending platforms such as MLOL or Emilib. A further one is the nature of the collections held (for example, technical or large-format texts such as maps and topographical charts, collections typical of public consultation, easily found in print as well, which do not justify an investment in digitisation).

The responses from a significant group of libraries nonetheless indicate a conviction that the offer of an (i)SDL service is essential for their operation and effectively meeting the needs of contemporary users. Such reasons highlight a proactive and future-oriented vision of the library's role. A central argument is the need to overcome geographical and temporal barriers, breaking down the limits imposed by distance and traditional opening hours, with (i)SDL becoming, among other things, an instrument of inclusion and learning support, guaranteeing equal opportunities for access to culture and information. Another aspect is linked to the enhancement and preservation of the library's heritage, especially in the case of rare, ancient, or unique holdings owned only by the library itself, without exposing them to the risk of damage resulting from direct physical consultation. Independence from external services and the creation of their own (i)SDL infrastructure are then considered long-term guarantees for the investments made and a way to break free from the costs of commercial solutions, also offering a service on out-of-print materials that publishers are no longer interested in reprinting.

Conversely, a group of participating libraries expresses uncertainty regarding the importance of offering an (i)SDL service, answering "don't know". The analysis of their reasons suggests a lack of familiarity with the system, a difficulty in assessing its immediate usefulness or its potential perspective in the future, and a lack of a clear current request from users.

B.3. Responses to Section III - LEGAL BARRIERS

This section focuses on the awareness of the participants around the legal framework governing (i)SDL. To understand the potential challenges and opportunities associated with the implementation of this digital lending model, specific questions are asked regarding the existence of legislative authorisation at the national level and the clarity of current legislation concerning the (i)SDL. The analysis of the responses collected aims to outline the legal barriers perceived by libraries and to provide an overview of the current regulatory framework.

Q15. Does your national copyright law or other legislation authorise (i)SDL, and under what conditions?

54.77% (241 units) declare that they are not aware of a specific authorisation in this regard.

37.5% (165 units), on the other hand, express the belief that the (i)SDL is authorised by national legislation.

5.23% (23 units) explicitly deny the existence of such authorisation, responding "No."

Finally, 2.50% (11 units) provide answers that do not allow a clear interpretation regarding the existence or non-existence of a legal authorisation for the (i)SDL, and so are deemed to be invalid.

Q15. Does your national copyright law or other legislation authorise (i)SDL, and under what conditions?

Most libraries state that they do not know how to answer the question of whether or not national copyright law authorises (i)SDL and under what conditions. The comments provided by some of these respondents offer interesting insights into the reasons for this uncertainty.

For example, they highlight the perceived coherence of the (i)SDL model with the European Directive 2006/115/EC, while admitting to not knowing the specific Italian legislation on the matter. This suggests an awareness of the principles underlying (i)SDL and a potential reference to the European regulatory framework, but a lack of clarity on its transposition and applicability at the national level.

Moreover, they underline the need for a joint assessment at the association level (AIB) or by territorial networks, suggesting that the legality of (i)SDL may require analysis and a collective stance from the organised library community.

Finally, the definition of the issue as "controversial" by other respondents underscores the legal complexity and the lack of a consensus on the legitimacy of (i)SDL in light of current copyright laws.

37.50% of libraries answer affirmatively to the question regarding whether (i)SDL is authorised at the national level.

Many responses emphasised the link between the authorisation of (i)SDL and the protection of copyright, expressly indicating the respect of the moral and economic rights of authors, ensuring that reproductions not authorised by rights holders are avoided (despite copyright law explicitly allowing this in many cases through exceptions). Moreover, quantitative limitations (such as the digitisation of a limited percentage of the work, often 15%), specific purposes (internal use, study and research purposes, access for persons with disabilities), and dissemination in a secure environment are required. The implementation of Digital Rights Management (DRM) is explicitly mentioned as a tool to guarantee the protection of digital copies and their self-deletion at the end of the loan period.

Other highlighted conditions concern the temporality and limitation of access, referring to

limited loan periods (often 15 days, in line with the practices of platforms like MLOL) and the need for temporary access, equating (i)SDL to the traditional lending of physical works ("one copy, one user").

Some comments emphasised the need for expert legal support to operate in compliance with complex and constantly evolving laws.

5.23% of libraries answer negatively because of the copyright law (Law 633/1941) that does not explicitly provide for the digital lending of physical copies owned by libraries. Some respondents note, in particular, that Article 69 specifically refers to the "lending of printed copies", thus excluding a direct application to digital. Others suggest that digital lending in Italy is mainly governed by private law agreements between library systems and publishers, rather than by a specific national law on (i)SDL.

Q16. How clear is your country's national copyright law or other legislation regarding (i)SDL?

26.36% (116 units) state that national legislation is not clear, while only 22.50% (99 units) consider them quite clear.

Most libraries, 48.64% (214 units), do not answer the question regarding the clarity of national legislation on (i)SDL.

Finally, only 2.50% (11 units) consider national legislation clear.

Q16. How clear is your country's national copyright law or other legislation regarding (i)SDL?

The analysis of the responses reveals a widespread perception of ambiguity and uncertainty. 26.36% of the respondents express a negative opinion, stating that national laws are not at all clear regarding (i)SDL. This finding highlights a potential significant barrier to the adoption of the model, as the lack of a defined legal framework can generate operational fears and uncertainties for libraries.

The majority of respondents, a considerable 48.64%, admit to not knowing how clear national legislation is concerning (i)SDL. This high percentage of uncertainty underscores a

lack of widespread awareness or understanding of the applicable legal framework, which could represent a brake on the exploration and implementation of services based on this model.

Only a small percentage, 2.50%, considers national legislation to be very clear in the matter of (i)SDL. This group may have conducted in-depth legal analyses or operate in specific contexts where the laws are perceived as more permissive.

B.4. Responses to Section IV - TECHNOLOGICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE BARRIERS

This section analyses the technological and structural challenges that participating libraries perceive as current or potential obstacles to the implementation of (i)SDL. Specific questions were asked regarding the technological barriers identified and the potential role of existing consortia or collaborations in overcoming these through the sharing of resources and infrastructure. The aim is to outline the landscape of practical limitations that could influence the adoption and scalability of (i)SDL within the library context.

Q17. What technological barriers has your library encountered – or might encounter – in implementing (i)SDL (Lack of adequate digitisation equipment, Lack of an adequate archiving system, Inadequate digital rights management (DRM) system or lack of technical protection measures know-how)?

(Please rate each barrier on a scale from 0 to 5, where 0= Don't know, 1 = Not a barrier and 5 = Major barrier). If you think there are other technological barriers, please indicate them below

A substantial majority of responding libraries, 167 out of 440, consider the lack of adequate digitisation equipment a major barrier (value 5) in implementing (i)SDL. Conversely, 42 libraries perceive this barrier as non-existent (value 1). A considerable portion falls into the intermediate categories: 55 select value 2, 65 select value 3, and 80 select value 4.

31 libraries select value 0, indicating they could not provide a valuation on this specific barrier.

Q17. What technological barriers has your library encountered – or might encounter – in implementing (i)SDL

The responses highlight a critical challenge for the widespread adoption of (i)SDL. The fact that over a third of the responding libraries identify this as a major barrier underscores the need to address the infrastructural disparities among institutions.

The presence of a smaller group that sees no barrier is encouraging, suggesting that some libraries are already well-equipped for digitisation. These institutions could potentially serve as early adopters and share their expertise and workflows.

However, the significant number of libraries positioned in the intermediate levels indicates a widespread need for investment and support in acquiring suitable digitisation equipment. This could involve financial aid programs, shared equipment initiatives at the consortium or regional level, or guidance on cost-effective digitisation solutions.

The number of libraries unable to assess this barrier (value 0) also warrants attention. It may be beneficial to provide more information and resources on the technological requirements of (i)SDL to ensure all libraries can accurately evaluate their readiness.

167 libraries out of 440 identify the lack of an adequate archiving system as a major barrier (value 5). 35 libraries consider this barrier non-existent (value 1). The intermediate values show a distribution: 43 libraries select value 2, 59 libraries select value 3, and 92 libraries select value 4. A notable 44 libraries select value 0, indicating an inability to assess the relevance or impact of this particular barrier.

Q17. What technological barriers has your library encountered – or might encounter – in implementing (i)SDL

While a small segment of libraries reports no issues with archiving, the large number identifying it as a major or moderate barrier suggests that this is a widespread concern that needs to be addressed for successful (i)SDL implementation. The ability to securely and efficiently store digitised materials is fundamental to the functionality and scalability of this lending model.

The number of "value 0" responses is also noteworthy. It suggests that a portion of libraries may not fully grasp the archiving demands associated with digital collections and lending. Educational initiatives and clearer guidelines on storage requirements for (i)SDL would be beneficial.

Therefore, it is fundamental to explore shared storage solutions at the consortium or regional level, provide guidance on cost-effective storage options, and potentially offer financial support for developing digital infrastructure. Addressing this barrier will be essential in enabling a greater number of libraries to participate in and benefit from (i)SDL.

The highest number of respondents, 202 libraries out of 440, identify an inadequate DRM system or a lack of know-how as a major barrier (value 5). A small number, 12 libraries, consider this barrier non-existent (value 1). The intermediate values show the following distribution: 29 libraries select value 2, 47 libraries select value 3, and 105 libraries select value 4. A notable 45 libraries select value 0, signifying an inability to assess this barrier.

Q17. What technological barriers has your library encountered – or might encounter – in implementing (i)SDL

Inadequate digital rights management (DRM) system or lack of technical protection measures know-how

Nearly half of the responding libraries consider this barrier a major one, underscoring the complexity and perceived difficulty associated with managing digital rights in a lending context.

The stark contrast between the high number of "value 5" responses and the very low number of "value 1" responses suggests that DRM is not a trivial issue for most libraries. The complexities of licensing, copyright, and the technical implementation of protection measures appear to be a significant source of concern.

The substantial number of libraries in the intermediate categories further reinforces the idea that while not insurmountable for all, DRM presents a considerable hurdle that requires attention and resources.

The relatively high number of "value 0" responses suggests a significant gap in understanding the critical role of DRM in digital lending. Educational initiatives focused on demystifying DRM, explaining its importance in rights management, and providing guidance on available solutions and best practices are crucial.

Q18. Is your library part of a consortium or collaboration that could share technological resources or infrastructures to enable (i)SDL? (Answer: Yes, No, Don't know). If you answered Yes, please specify which consortium or collaboration.

39.54% (174 units) of respondents state that they are not aware of this information, 42.73% (188 units) state that they are part of a consortium or have collaborations, while 17.73% (78 units) state that they do not have any form of participation in consortia or collaborations to implement i(SDL).

Q18. Is your library part of a consortium or collaboration that could share technological resources or infrastructures to enable (i)SDL?

Most libraries state that they are part of a consortium or have ongoing collaborations that could be leveraged to share the resources necessary for the implementation of (i)SDL. This data highlights a significant potential for the adoption of the model, as the sharing of costs, expertise, and infrastructure could make (i)SDL more accessible, especially for libraries with limited resources.

However, a considerable percentage admits to not being aware of this information: this could indicate a lack of internal communication within the organization, a low awareness of the potential opportunities offered by existing consortia or collaborations, or the need for a more in-depth investigation into the actual possibilities of sharing resources for (i)SDL within their networks.

Finally, for the minority of libraries that state they do not have any form of participation in consortia or collaborations specifically oriented towards the implementation of (i)SDL, the adoption of the model could represent a greater challenge, requiring more substantial individual investments or the search for new forms of collaboration.

Among the 188 libraries that answer affirmatively to the question, 184 then specify which consortium or collaboration they are part of.

Participation in regional, provincial, or local library consortia is the most frequently mentioned form of collaboration. These systems, such as the Regional Library System (Marche), SDIAF in the Florence area, the SBV (Valle d'Aosta), the Lecco area Library System, the Cremona Library Network, the Lodi Library System, the Lucca Library Network, Brianzabiblioteche, the Bergamo Library Network (RBBG), the Biella Library Hub, the Seriate Laghi Library System, the Bassa Bresciana Centrale Library System (RBBC), the Sulcis Interurban Library System (SBIS), Opac Sardegna - Rete Indaco, and many others at the municipal and provincial levels, often already share management software, online catalogs, and, in some cases, digital lending platforms, such as MLOL and Emilib. Although these latter platforms are not native (i)SDL, their existing infrastructure, digital rights management, and user familiarity

could represent a starting point or a model from which to draw inspiration for the implementation of (i)SDL at the consortium level.

Membership in SBN (Servizio Bibliotecario Nazionale) hubs, both at the university level (such as the UBO Hug, the CAG Hub, the SBN UPO Hub, the TSA FVG Hub, the UTO Hub, and the Research Bibliographic Hub) and at the territorial level, represents another important form of collaboration. These hubs often coordinate services and resources at a national or regional level and could facilitate the adoption of shared standards and technologies for (i)SDL.

Other interesting forms of collaboration are those with the Libraries of the University of Piemonte, the Fondazione San Bonaventura APS, participation in SHARE (Interuniversity Convention for the integration of library and documentation services), university presses through platforms such as DADI_PRESS. These more targeted collaborations could offer opportunities for (i)SDL pilot projects or for the sharing of specific skills.

Finally, the mention of specialized networks such as NILDE (for Document Delivery) and Bibliosan (for biomedical libraries) suggests that even in specific contexts, forms of collaboration exist that could evolve towards the sharing of (i)SDL infrastructure for particular materials.

B.5. Responses to Section V - RISK OF OPPOSITION

The section dedicated to the 'risk of opposition' aimed to investigate the resistance of respondents' institutions (e.g., staff or administration) to implementing (i)SDL, whether libraries are reluctant to implement (i)SDL because of concerns about potential legal actions from publishers or authors or potential technological barriers, and how the publishing industry would respond to the idea of (i)SDL.

The data analysis will provide a detailed overview of the results.

Q19. Do you face resistance from within your institution (e.g., staff or administration) to implementing (i)SDL?

The majority of the respondents 50,90% (224) replied that they don't know if the library would meet resistance to (i)SDL implementation by the staff or the administration, while 9,09% (40) replied yes and 40% (176) no.

Q19. Do you face resistance from within your institution (e.g., staff or administration) to implementing (i)SDL?

The responses to question 19 reveal a notable degree of uncertainty regarding potential resistance within libraries to the implementation of (i)SDL. These results suggest that more than half of the participants lack clear insight into the internal dynamics or decision-making processes concerning (i)SDL implementation. The relatively low percentage of affirmative responses (9,09%) indicates that explicit resistance is not widespread. However, this must be weighed against the high percentage of "don't know" responses, which limits the strength of this conclusion. It is possible that resistance exists but is not perceived or acknowledged by all staff, particularly if it occurs at administrative or managerial levels.

The 40% who reported no resistance suggest that in many libraries, the environment is receptive or at least neutral toward (i)SDL adoption. This is a positive sign and could provide a foundation for further implementation and staff engagement.

In summary, while overt resistance does not appear to be prevalent, the high level of uncertainty among respondents points to a need for improved awareness, internal communication, and involvement of broader library personnel in (i)SDL-related discussions and decision-making.

If you answered "Yes" to the previous question, please specify

Of the 40 respondents who had answered "yes" to question n. 19, 35 indicated the reasons. From the free-text responses, the same barriers as previously indicated in the report arise. A predominant concern is the lack of financial support, both for acquiring necessary technology and for covering potential copyright costs. Several libraries report that no budget is allocated by the administration for such services, making implementation unfeasible. Many respondents highlight a shortage of staff, with existing personnel already overloaded or unqualified. In some cases, libraries are run by volunteers or a single librarian without digital skills, often due to age or lack of training. There are infrastructural limitations, such as the absence of internet-connected PCs or suitable spaces for digital services, especially in specific contexts like ecclesiastical or prison libraries. Respondents note a lack of political will and administrative disinterest. Some mention governance issues or a general resistance to change, with no long-term vision for library development. Concerns include copyright

uncertainty, fear of legal violations, and user resistance. In a few cases, respondents simply state that the service is not of interest to their community.

Q20. In your opinion, are libraries in your country reluctant to implement (i)SDL because of concerns about potential legal actions from publishers or authors?

The majority of respondents 52,50% (231) replied they don't know if libraries in Italy are reluctant to implement (i)SDL because of concerns about potential legal actions from publishers or authors. 27,70% (122) of respondents replied that they are reluctant for the mentioned reasons, while 15,60% (69) said they don't.

4,09 (18) of the respondents answered "other", indicating different types of comments.

Of the 18 who responded "other" to question n. 20, 16 respondents indicated further specification. What emerges from the free-text responses is the lack of knowledge about the management of these resources and the lack of support from the relevant administrations, economic obstacles, technological barriers and lack of dedicated staff. It also emerges that there is little knowledge of the position of libraries other than one's own and uncertainty about legislation, as well as the perception that perhaps some publishers might object but probably not all of them, plus the need to differentiate by type of loan and embargo.

Q20. In your opinion, are libraries in your country reluctant to implement (i)SDL because of concerns about potential legal actions from publishers or authors?

Q21. In your opinion, are libraries in your country reluctant to implement (i)SDL because of concerns about potential technological barriers?

A large portion of respondents (46,59% (205)) are uncertain whether technological barriers stand in the way of (i)SDL implementation in Italian libraries. One-third 33,40% (147) believe such reluctance exists, while 17,04 (75) do not.

The remaining 2,90% (13) offered alternative views. This highlights a widespread lack of clarity and possibly limited visibility into the technical capabilities of libraries.

The responses suggest that technological barriers are closely linked to financial and training deficits. Libraries report outdated equipment, lack of DRM systems, and insufficient staff training as major challenges. Several comments emphasise that without state or regional support, implementing (i)SDL is unlikely. Some respondents believe these barriers are surmountable, while others point to limited user demand as a reason for low prioritisation. Overall, the data highlights a mix of technical, economic, and strategic limitations.

Q21. In your opinion, are libraries in your country reluctant to implement (i)SDL because of concerns about potential technological barriers?

Q22. How would the publishing industry in your country respond to the idea of (i)SDL?

The majority of the respondents (53,40% (235)) replied they don't know, while 35,60% (157) answered that industry is against (i)SDL (10% (44)) of the participants said they believe the industry is neutral and the remaining 0,90% (4) said that the industry is strongly in favor.

Q22. How would the publishing industry in your country respond to the idea of (i)SDL?

Strongly supportive Neutral Opposed I don't know

The responses to the question on how the publishing industry would react to the idea of (i)SDL reveal a general uncertainty or scepticism. A majority — 53,40% (235 respondents) — indicated they don't know, suggesting either a lack of information, limited public debate on (i)SDL, or low visibility of the topic in the national publishing context.

A significant portion — 35.60% (157 respondents) — stated that the industry is against (i)SDL, indicating a prevailing perception of resistance, potentially due to concerns about copyright, control over rights, or economic models.

Only 10% (44 respondents) viewed the industry as neutral, showing that few consider the publishing sector as undecided or balanced on the issue. A negligible minority — 0.90% (4 respondents) — believe the industry is strongly in favor, pointing to rare instances of support or openness.

B.6. Responses To Section VI - HUMAN RESOURCES

The section dedicated to 'human barriers' aimed at investigating if the library has access to legal expertise to address copyright and (i)SDL-related issues, if the library staff received training or guidance on (i)SDL's legal aspects, and if such legal training or guidance is necessary. Furthermore, this section investigates whether the library has access to technological expertise to address (i)SDL-related issues, or if its staff had received training or guidance on (i)SDL's technological aspects (e.g., digital rights management, archiving systems, etc.), and if such technological training or guidance is necessary.

The data analysis will provide a detailed overview of libraries' issues related to human resources for the implementation of (i)SDL.

Q23. Does your library have access to legal expertise to address copyright and (i)SDL-related issues?

Q23. Does your library have access to legal expertise to address copyright and (i)SDL-related issues?

■ Yes, we have specialized staff or legal counsel
 ■ No, we don't have the necessary legal support
 ■ Don't know
 ■ Other

Question 23 opens the section on surveying specific legal expertise within libraries on copyright and SDL. Only 6% of libraries say they have specific expertise within their staff or can count on the support of specialised legal counsel. In contrast, about 70% say they cannot count on legal support and 21% do not know how to answer the question. The “Other” option was selected by only a few participants (4%). Very often the presence of legal offices at the University level, to which the library can turn, is indicated as representing a form of specific outside advice, accessible upon request. However, the most interesting finding from this small group of responses is the realisation that targeted expertise on these issues is needed, which is not always present within legal offices that, in most cases, deal with other matters.

Q24. Has your library staff received training or guidance on (i)SDL's legal aspects?

Q24. Has your library staff received training or guidance on (i)SDL's legal aspects?

■ Yes, full training
 ■ Yes, but limited training
 ■ Ongoing training
 ■ No training
 ■ Don't know

In line with the responses to the previous question, 83% of the participants say that library staff have not received any training on the legal aspects related to (i)SDL, while 9% report having received non-exhaustive training and only 2% of library staff have started training, which is still ongoing. Only one participant claims to have received full training on the subject (0% in the graph). The percentage of “I don't know” corresponds to 6%.

If you answer “No” or “In progress” to the question above, please explain any challenges related to human resources:

Participants could give a reason for their response if they selected either the “No training” option or the “Ongoing training” option in question 24. In most cases, 54% of this group justified their response by attributing the lack of training to the two main problems that have always plagued libraries: lack of staff (or precariousness of tenure) and lack of dedicated funds. These two “chronic” problems prevent training from being carried out comprehensively and systematically. Several participants also pointed out that library services are carried out by volunteers or unskilled staff who work with libraries but perform many other tasks and have neither interest nor time to devote to library-specific training. Others pointed out the lack of interest of institutions (local and otherwise) in libraries. In these cases, the training became an individual choice of who is willing to incur costs and devote extra work time to this activity. Only a small minority claim to have no interest in copyright/(i)SDL as a topic, while the importance of training librarians on these issues or at least having qualified outside support is stressed in most cases.

Q25. Do you think such legal training or guidance is necessary?

Q25. Do you think such legal training or guidance is necessary?

As can be seen in the graph, the interest of librarians in the copyright/SDL issue, anticipated in the comments to question 24, is confirmed. In this case, the request for their opinion on the subject was directly phrased, and as many as 77% said they thought such focused training was necessary; only 4% saw no need for it, while 19% said they did not know how to answer the question.

Q26. Does your library have access to technological expertise to address (i)SDL-related issues?

Q26. Does your library have access to technological expertise to address (i)SDL-related issues?

88% of respondents replied they did not have the appropriate technological skills to perform (i)SDL. Only 9% said they had the necessary skills, while 18% said they could not answer

the question. In the other group (4%) there were answers not containing a YES/NO answer but rather explanations, more or less articulated, from which information on individual specificities emerged, including ongoing technological training, skills partially already present but lacking infrastructure, issues around technological support not being managed at library level but at the institution level and, once again, the shortage of (specialised) personnel, equipment and funds.

Q27. Has your library staff received training or guidance on (i)SDL's technological aspects (e.g., digital rights management, archiving systems, etc.)?

Q27. Has your library staff received training or guidance on (i)SDL's technological aspects (e.g., digital rights management, archiving systems, etc.)?

■ Yes, full training
 ■ Yes, but limited training
 ■ Ongoing training
 ■ No training
 ■ Don't know

Question 27 asks how well trained librarians are in the technological/management aspects of (i)SDL. This question complements Question 24, which raised the same reflection from the legal point of view, while Question 27 deals specifically with technological training. The selection options proposed in the two questions are the same and the answers reflect, in essence, the same percentages. The item "No training" is chosen by 79% against 83% in question 24 and the item "Yes, but limited training" is chosen by 13% of the participants against 9% in question 24. The slight decrease in the first item is reflected in the small increase in the second and the difference is probably due to generic responses on technological readiness and not targeted at SDL management.

If you answer "No" or "In progress" to the question above, please explain any challenges related to human resources:

Again, participants could justify if they selected the "No training" or "Ongoing training" options when answering question 27. In this case, the reason was given by 40% of the respondents. The given reasons also follow in practice what was expressed by the participants earlier: substantial interest in the development of targeted training courses and identification of problems related to institutions' lack of interest in libraries, as well as staff and funding shortages.

Q28. Do you think such technological training or guidance is necessary?

Q28. Do you think such technological training or guidance is necessary?

Question 28 closes section B.6 and complements question 25, which raises the same reflection, but from the legal point of view. The selection options proposed in the two questions are the same and the answers reflect the same percentages: 77% said they thought such focused training was necessary; only 4% saw no need for it, while 19% said they did not know how to answer the question.

B.7. Responses To Section VII - FINANCIAL BARRIERS

The section dedicated to 'financial barriers' aimed to investigate whether the library has adequate financial resources to implement (i)SDL, and if digitisation tools and DRM systems are affordable for the library.

The data analysis will provide a detailed overview of libraries' issues related to financial barriers for the implementation of (i)SDL.

Q29. Does your library have adequate financial resources to implement (i)SDL?

The majority of the respondents - 65,60% (289) - replied that they don't have adequate financial resources to implement (i)SDL, while only 6,30% (28) responded positively. A big percentage (27,90% (123)) declared that they don't know if they have adequate resources for this purpose.

Q29. Does your library have adequate financial resources to implement (i)SDL?

The response shows significant financial challenges in implementing (i)SDL, with 65,60% of respondents indicating a lack of adequate resources and only 6,30% confirming sufficient funding. Notably, 27,90% were uncertain about their financial capacity, suggesting a lack of clarity or communication regarding budget allocation. Overall, the data points to widespread unpreparedness, either due to actual budget limitations or institutional opacity, underscoring the need for clearer financial planning and support structures to enable effective (i)SDL implementation.

Q30. Are digitisation tools and DRM systems affordable for the library?

The majority of the respondents 57,50% (253) replied that digitisation tools and DRM systems are not affordable for the library, while 15,40 (68) replied that they are affordable. A big percentage of respondents 27,04% (119) didn't know about it.

Q30. Are digitisation tools and DRM systems affordable for the library?

■ Yes ■ No ■ Don't know

The response shows that digitisation tools and DRM systems are largely perceived as unaffordable indicating cost as a barrier. Only a few percent consider them affordable, while 27,04% are unsure, suggesting limited awareness or involvement in procurement decisions. This points to both financial and informational challenges, highlighting the need for increased funding and better communication around digital infrastructure in libraries.

B.8. Responses To Section VIII - OTHER FACTORS

The section dedicated to 'other factors' aimed at investigating whether the library's staff would benefit from more information/training events on (i)SDL, what steps national policymakers should take to facilitate (i)SDL adoption in libraries, if (i)SDL will become more relevant for libraries in the future, and whether the library's (i)SDL system would integrate with existing catalogues and platforms. Furthermore, it explored whether the library can secure users' personal and digital content data by providing (i)SDL, and what are the negative consequences of not providing (i)SDL.

The data analysis will provide a detailed overview of other libraries' issues for the implementation of (i)SDL.

Q31. Would you or your staff benefit from more information/formative events on (i)SDL?

The majority of the respondents 69,30% (305) confirm they would benefit from more information or formative events on the topic, while only 4,50% (20) replied they wouldn't and a large percentage of respondents 26,10% (115) don't know.

Q31. Would you or your staff benefit from more information/formative events on (i)SDL?

The response indicates a strong interest in further education on (i)SDL, with the majority of respondents expressing a need for more information or training opportunities. Only 4,50% see no benefit, while 26,10% are uncertain, suggesting that awareness and engagement with the topic could be improved. Overall, the data highlights a clear demand for capacity-building initiatives to support (i)SDL understanding and implementation.

Q32. In your opinion, what steps should national policymakers take to facilitate (i)SDL adoption in libraries?

Q32. In your opinion, what steps should national policymakers take to facilitate (i)SDL adoption in libraries?

Summary of policy suggestions for (i)SDL adoption (in English)

Here is a summary of the main categories that emerged from respondents' suggestions on what national policymakers should do to support (i)SDL adoption in libraries. The most

frequent suggestions included training, financial support, and updating copyright legislation.

- Training
- Don't know/Uncertain
- Funding/Economic Resources
- Legislation/Copyright Law
- Technical Support/Infrastructure
- Staffing
- National Platform/Coordination
- Agreements with Publishers

The analysis of policy recommendations for supporting (i)SDL adoption reveals a clear set of priorities and concerns among library professionals regarding what national policymakers should do to support the implementation of independent secure digital lending ((i)SDL) systems in libraries.

Training emerges as the most frequently mentioned need, accounting for over a quarter of all categorised responses (26.1%). This suggests that many respondents perceive a critical lack of knowledge and skills among library staff, particularly regarding digital technologies, copyright management, and system implementation. Calls for structured training programmes—often mentioned in conjunction with legal and technical aspects—highlight the sector’s desire for capacity-building as a foundational step.

Equally notable is the share of respondents (17.4%) who reported uncertainty or lack of knowledge ("Don't know/Uncertain") about what policy actions would be appropriate. This may reflect a broader issue: a lack of communication, awareness, or engagement with national-level discussions on digital lending. It underscores the importance of informational outreach and consultation, particularly with smaller or less digitally-equipped libraries.

Another 17.4% of responses point to the need for increased funding and economic resources. Respondents frequently mention that without targeted financial support, libraries cannot invest in the necessary infrastructure, staff, or digital resources to make (i)SDL viable. This aligns with earlier concerns in the survey about limited budgets and administrative reluctance to prioritise digital innovation.

Closely related to this is the demand for clear and updated copyright legislation, which appears in 13% of responses. Uncertainty around legal frameworks is seen as a major

obstacle, and participants call for reforms that define the scope of digital lending rights more precisely, particularly in the context of educational and public-access use.

Finally, technical support and infrastructure development also account for 13% of suggestions. Respondents note the need for national platforms, shared systems, and tools that could ease the burden on individual institutions. A few respondents also stress the importance of establishing inter-library coordination and developing centralised services or agreements with publishers.

In summary, the responses outline a coherent set of needs: training, funding, legal clarity, and infrastructure, along with more inclusive dialogue between policymakers and library stakeholders. These elements form a roadmap for enabling widespread and equitable adoption of (i)SDL across the Italian library system.

Q33. Do you think (i)SDL will become more relevant for libraries in the future?

The majority of the respondents 62,20% (274) replied that (i)SDL will become more relevant for libraries in the future while only a very small percentage of 2,90% (13) of respondents don't think that. 34,70% (153) of the respondents don't know.

Q33. Do you think (i)SDL will become more relevant for libraries in the future?

The majority suggests a strong belief in the growing relevance of (i)SDL for libraries, indicating forward-looking awareness and recognition of its potential impact. The minimal opposition (2,90%) reinforces this trend, though the relatively high percentage of uncertain respondents (34,70%) points to a need for clearer communication about the future role and benefits of (i)SDL in library services.

Please specify why

Of the 274 respondents who replied “yes” to question Q33 178 respondents justified their responses as follows. First, many respondents reflect on the ongoing digital transformation in society. As digital technologies become more embedded in everyday life, library users are growing accustomed to remote and immediate access to content. This shift in expectation is

particularly evident among younger generations, who are often more fluent in using digital tools for learning, reading, and research. In this context, digital lending is seen not as a trend, but as a necessary evolution of library services.

Closely linked to this is the emphasis on accessibility and inclusivity. Numerous comments highlight how (i)SDL can reduce barriers for those who are unable to visit libraries in person—whether due to distance, physical limitations, or other constraints. Digital lending is thus viewed as a tool that supports the broader mission of libraries to democratise knowledge and serve diverse communities more effectively.

Another theme that emerges is the preservation and operational value of (i)SDL. By enabling the digital circulation of rare, delicate, or high-demand materials, libraries can better safeguard their collections while extending access. Respondents also point out that digital services can help streamline processes, optimise space, and enhance overall efficiency.

Many participants describe the shift toward digital not as a possibility, but as an inevitable development. They refer to it as something that is “already underway” or even “already a reality,” especially in the wake of the pandemic, which accelerated the adoption of remote learning and digital access to information.

Finally, some respondents underscore the strategic importance of embracing (i)SDL. For libraries to remain relevant and responsive to contemporary user needs, they must evolve alongside technological and societal changes. In this view, (i)SDL is not merely an additional service, but a cornerstone of what the library of the future must become—accessible, flexible, and digitally connected.

Among the small group of respondents who do not believe that (i)SDL will become more relevant in the future, several key perspectives emerge that help contextualise their position. A recurring point is that digital lending services are already well established through existing national or regional platforms. These systems, often managed centrally and already integrated into library networks, are perceived as sufficient to meet current user needs. From this viewpoint, introducing or investing in an additional model like (i)SDL is seen as potentially redundant, especially when resources are limited and priorities must be carefully assessed.

Another theme that emerges is the enduring value of print materials and physical library spaces. Some respondents emphasise the cultural and emotional connection users still feel toward printed books—describing the experience of leafing through a physical volume as more engaging than reading on a screen. Moreover, they highlight the role of public libraries not just as service providers, but as community spaces where books facilitate human connection, encounters, and social interaction—functions that digital lending cannot replicate.

A few comments suggest that while (i)SDL might have a role to play, it would be most relevant for specific types of libraries, such as those preserving historical or rare materials. For mainstream public libraries, which already rely on broader digital collections provided by external services, the added value of developing independent digital lending infrastructure is questioned.

Finally, one respondent raises a concern about declining reading habits among young people, casting doubt on whether further digital access will actually lead to greater engagement with reading.

Of the 153 who replied “don’t know” to Q33, about if (i)SDL will become more relevant for libraries in the future, 42 provided further information as follows. For many, the response “I don’t know” stems from a lack of familiarity with the concept of (i)SDL, its legal implications, or its practical implementation in Italy. Several respondents openly acknowledge not having enough information or experience to make a judgment, pointing to the need for clearer communication, training, and dialogue on the topic within the library sector. Others take a more contextual stance, noting that the relevance of (i)SDL depends heavily on the type of library, its users, and its collections. Some emphasise that small public or children’s libraries, or libraries serving a readership still attached to physical books, may not be the ideal settings for (i)SDL. Conversely, a few respondents recognise its potential value for academic or research libraries, especially those handling rare or non-circulating materials.

Several contributions also frame the future of (i)SDL as conditional—dependent on broader factors such as the evolution of copyright law, the level of institutional investment, and the capacity of library staff to adopt new tools. Some express concern that economic and political priorities, as well as market-driven approaches, may limit the feasibility or fairness of such systems, especially for smaller or underfunded libraries.

Interestingly, a few respondents reflect more broadly on the uncertain future of reading itself. While acknowledging the increasing presence of digital platforms, they question whether digital reading will ever fully replace the cultural and emotional attachment to print. One respondent frames the dilemma in terms of competing models of the future library—whether as a repository of physical materials or a digitally networked service hub. In summary, the “I don’t know” responses reflect not just a knowledge gap, but a wider set of structural, practical, and philosophical uncertainties. They reveal a landscape in which (i)SDL is still emerging as a concept, and its future relevance is seen as contingent upon legal clarity, user needs, institutional support, and a shared vision of what libraries should become.

Q34. Could the library’s (i)SDL system integrate with existing catalogues and platforms?

The majority of respondents 58,10% (256) replied affirmatively, while only 2,04% (9) say no and 39,70% (175) don’t how an (i)SDL system would integrate with existing catalogues and platforms.

Q34. Could the library's (i)SDL system integrate with existing catalogues and platforms?

The majority of respondents believe that the library's (i)SDL system could integrate with existing catalogues and platforms, indicating optimism or existing compatibility. However, the high percentage of respondents who are unsure suggests limited technical awareness or communication regarding integration capabilities. The very low negative response (2%) points to minimal perceived barriers, but the uncertainty highlights a need for clearer information and technical assessment.

Q35. Can the library secure users' personal and digital content data by providing (i)SDL?

The majority of the respondents - 53,10% (234) - replied that they don't know if the library can secure users' personal and digital content data by providing (i)SDL, while a big percentage 40,60% (179) think that the library can secure them and only 6,10% (27) think that the library can't secure them.

Q35. Can the library secure users' personal and digital content data by providing (i)SDL?

The response reveals significant uncertainty, with the majority of respondents unsure whether (i)SDL can ensure data security, suggesting a lack of awareness or confidence in current practices. While 40,60% believe the library can secure user data, the relatively low 6,10% expressing doubt indicates limited concern but also highlights the need for clearer policies, communication, and training on data protection within (i)SDL systems.

Q36. What are the negative consequences of not providing (i)SDL? (More than one answer possible)

Concerning the costs of not developing (i)SDL and wider eLending, 33,33% of the respondents (273) replied that the library would not be able to allow a user to read a book if he/she could not go to the library personally and the publisher has not provided an e-book version of the book. 27,50% (226) of the respondents replied that the library's services risked becoming less attractive compared to those of other libraries or digital platforms. 10,10% (83) of the respondents replied that users would be less likely to engage with the library's services. 9,40% (77) of the respondents replied that the library may face increased pressure to offer digital access options. 6,70% (55) of the respondents replied that the library could lose its relationship with users. 6,10% (50) of the respondents replied that they don't know. 4,60% (38) of the respondents replied that there are no negative consequences of not providing (i)SDL.

2% (17) replied "other" and 9 of them provided comments. The lack of (i)SDL is not widely perceived as a pressing issue among these respondents. Most either delegate digital services to external platforms, serve niche research audiences, or do not consider (i)SDL a strategic priority. However, concerns about user detachment and reduced personal interaction suggest that digital lending models, including (i)SDL, should be implemented thoughtfully, balancing accessibility with the relational dimension of library services.

Q36. What are the negative consequences of not providing (i)SDL?

- The library cannot allow a user to read a book if he/she cannot go to the library personally and the publisher has not provided an e-book version of the book
- The library's services become less competitive than other libraries or digital platforms
- Users are less likely to engage with the library's services
- The library may face increased pressure to offer digital access options
- The library loses its relationship with users
- Don't know
- There are no negative consequences of not providing (i)SDL
- Other

Number of Responses

C. Summary of the results of the questionnaire

B1. Profile of Respondents

Most respondents represent public libraries (56%), followed by academic libraries (20%), with school, national. Academic libraries, although fewer, appear more engaged with the iSDL topic relative to their total number. In terms of collections, nearly all libraries report holding monographs (98%), while serials (59%), multimedia (46%), and archival materials (32%) are also common. Fewer libraries hold e-only resources (23%) or public domain/out-of-copyright materials (12%).

Regarding collection size, 62% of libraries have a large or very large physical collection, while 68% report a small digital collection, indicating a lag in digital development. This is further reflected in staffing: 73% of libraries lack dedicated personnel for digital services. The issue is most pronounced in public libraries (80%), while academic libraries show a better ratio, with 51% having dedicated staff.

B.2 Digital Lending

The analysis of the surveyed libraries reveals a mixed landscape regarding digital lending. While the importance of digital resources is acknowledged, a significant portion of libraries

do not currently offer digital lending services (62,05%). Among those that do (36,14%), the majority (86,79%) limit it to specific resources, indicating a cautious approach likely driven by budget, copyright, or perceived demand. Only a small minority (10,06%) lend their entire collection digitally.

The adoption of the specific (i)SDL model for digitising physical works for lending is very limited (3,86%). This is attributed to copyright concerns, technical complexity, costs, and potentially a lack of strategic prioritisation.

Libraries reporting high demand for (i)SDL (4,32%) tend to be highly specialised institutions, serving users like remote university students and often possessing unique or hard-to-find materials. Moderate demand (17,50%) is often linked to poor communication, lack of equipment and dedicated staff, and, in humanities fields, a lower availability of digital content from publishers.

Forecasts for (i)SDL demand show cautious optimism, with most expecting a marginal increase (34,09%).

Most libraries consider (i)SDL important but not essential (56,36%). They recognise the benefits for remote and disabled users and for expanding collections without physical constraints. However, they often cite current low demand due to user demographics (elderly, children, specialised users preferring physical consultation), a preference for print, or familiarity with other digital platforms like MLOL.

B.3 Legal Barriers

Responses reveal significant uncertainty and a lack of clarity among libraries regarding the national legal framework governing (i)SDL.

Indeed, a large majority (54,77%) do not know how to answer regarding the existence of authorisation, with some citing a lack of knowledge of specific national legislation despite awareness of the European Directive on the matter.

Libraries are hesitant to implement a service when its legality is unclear, leading to operational fears and hindering innovation.

Although a significant portion of libraries (37,50%) believe that (i)SDL is authorised, comments reveal a heterogeneous understanding, often tied to specific conditions and interpretations of national copyright law.

The lack of familiarity with (i)SDL in some contexts suggests the need for greater information and discussion within the Italian library community.

Moreover, the low percentage of those who consider the national legal framework on (i)SDL "quite clear" (22,50%) and the even lower percentage of those who consider it "very clear" (2,50%) suggests that, even where a normative basis is perceived, grey areas and margins of interpretation remain.

B.4 Technological and Infrastructure Barriers

The clear prevalence of high ratings (4 and 5) underscores how technological barriers in general represent a significant obstacle for a large portion of the libraries interested in implementing (i)SDL.

Therefore, overcoming the identified technological barriers appears as a fundamental step to enable a wider adoption of (i)SDL, requiring a concrete commitment in terms of resources and skills.

The significant percentage (42,73%) of libraries that are part of consortia or have collaborations suggests fertile ground for the adoption of (i)SDL, taking advantage of existing synergies not only to reduce individual costs, but also to promote the sharing of best practices and technical skills, joint staff training and the creation of working groups dedicated to this digital lending model.

The strong presence of consortia and collaborations in the Italian library landscape represents a key asset for the implementation of (i)SDL. However, it is crucial that these consortia and networks actively consider (i)SDL as a potential shared service, defining common strategies, identifying appropriate technological solutions, and providing technical and legal support to participating libraries.

B.5 Risk of oppositions

Responses reveal that explicit opposition to (i)SDL is limited, but uncertainty is widespread. A majority of respondents (over 50%) are unsure whether resistance exists within their institutions, pointing to gaps in communication and involvement. Only 9% reported clear internal resistance, while 40% said there was none. Where resistance is acknowledged, it stems mainly from lack of funding, staff, infrastructure, and digital skills—particularly in smaller or under-resourced libraries.

Legal fears also play a role: 28% believe concerns about lawsuits from publishers or authors discourage implementation, though 52% say they don't know. Technological barriers are seen as a factor by 33%, but again, nearly half (47%) are uncertain. As for the publishing industry, 36% perceive it as opposed to (i)SDL, while a majority (53%) say they don't know its stance, and only 10% believe it to be neutral or supportive. Overall, the key obstacle is not overt resistance, but a pervasive lack of clarity. Bridging this knowledge gap is essential to move forward.

B.6 Human resources

The results highlight significant gaps in both legal and technological capacities within libraries for managing (i)SDL services. Only 6% of libraries have access to legal expertise, while 70% lack such support and 21% are unsure. Similarly, 83% report no legal training for staff, and only 2% have training in progress. Despite this, 77% believe legal training is necessary. On the technological side, 88% of libraries lack the required technical expertise for SDL, and 79% report no staff training in this area. Only 13% have received limited technological training. Again, 77% consider such training essential. The main barriers identified include staff shortages and lack of funding, repeatedly cited as core issues preventing both legal and technical training.

B.7 Financial Barriers

The vast majority of respondents (66%) report that their libraries lack the financial resources needed to implement (i)SDL, while only 6% say they have sufficient funding. A further 28% are unsure, revealing both real budget constraints and limited transparency around financial planning.

When asked about the affordability of digitisation tools and DRM systems, 58% say they are

not affordable, while just 15% find them accessible, and 27% are uncertain. These figures reflect not only widespread financial limitations but also a lack of awareness or involvement in budgeting and procurement.

Overall, both cost and communication emerge as major barriers to (i)SDL adoption, underscoring the need for increased investment and clearer institutional strategies.

B.8 Others

There is strong interest in further education on (i)SDL: 69% of respondents say they or their staff would benefit from more information or training, while 26% are unsure and only 5% see no need. This highlights a clear demand for capacity-building initiatives. When asked what policymakers should prioritise, respondents most frequently cited training (26.1%), followed by funding (17.4%), legal reform (13%), and technical support (13%). Notably, 17.4% were unsure, reflecting a need for greater awareness and dialogue between policymakers and library professionals.

Looking ahead, 62% believe (i)SDL will become more relevant for libraries, while 35% are unsure and just 3% disagree. Those in favour cite digital access, inclusivity, and evolving user expectations, especially post-pandemic. Technical integration appears feasible: 58% believe (i)SDL could integrate with current systems, though 40% are unsure, signaling a need for better communication on infrastructure. Only 2% foresee technical incompatibility.

Data security is another area of uncertainty: 53% don't know if user data can be safely handled via (i)SDL, while 41% think it can, and just 6% think it cannot. This indicates low concern, but also a knowledge gap in digital privacy practices.

On the consequences of not adopting (i)SDL, 33% say users miss out if a book isn't available in person or as an ebook. 28% believe libraries risk falling behind other platforms, while 10% foresee lower user engagement. Only 5% believe there are no negative consequences.

In sum, libraries show growing interest in (i)SDL but remain hampered by uncertainty about policies, infrastructure, and future relevance. Strategic investment in training, funding, and legal clarity will be key to meaningful adoption.

IV. Conclusions

The survey paints a vivid picture of Italian libraries, highlighting the prevailing sense of the need for a shift to adapt their mission to the digital world, including the provision of (i)SDL services. While digital lending and specifically (i)SDL is broadly seen as promising and potentially transformative, adoption remains limited. Public libraries dominate in number but lag in digital readiness, while academic institutions, though fewer, show higher engagement. A striking digital divide is evident: most libraries have large physical collections but lack digital resources, infrastructure, and specialised staff.

Legal uncertainty, technological gaps, and financial constraints form a trio of persistent barriers. The (i)SDL model is little known, often misunderstood, and rarely implemented, primarily due to confusion over its legal basis and the complexity of digitisation systems. Yet a strong undercurrent of interest runs through the responses: libraries recognise the benefits of (i)SDL, particularly for remote access, inclusivity, and long-term relevance.

With strategic coordination, especially through library consortia, (i)SDL could evolve from a marginal practice into a shared and sustainable service, expanding digital access while safeguarding cultural collections for all.

Crucially, the data reveal not resistance, but hesitation rooted in limited knowledge, skills, and resources. The solution is clear: meaningful progress depends on investment in legal and technical training, clearer policies, stronger institutional support, and a legislative reform to align with and implement the principles established by the Court of Justice of the European Union in its ruling of 10 November 2016 (Case C-174/15) on e-lending by libraries in the EU, which provides the legal foundation for Independent Secure Digital Lending (i)SDL.

Appendix A - Questionnaire

Questionnaire on the barriers to the adoption of (independent) Secure Digital Lending (iSDL): Legal, technical, and operational challenges.

This questionnaire results from an initiative of [Knowledge Rights 21](#) (KR21) aimed at gathering information from libraries in Italy, Poland, and Spain concerning (independent) **Secure Digital Lending (iSDL) — e-lending based on paper books digitised by libraries where some protection measures are adopted to prevent non-legitimate uses (for instance, measures to limitate the lending time, to prevent downloading, etc. often named DRM Digital Rights Management Systems)**⁸. It investigates the legal, technical, and other barriers that influence the potential for further adoption of (i)SDL.

The partners of this research project are:

Italy: [STUDIO LEGALE DDA](#); [CLAKP](#) (Copyright Law and Access to Knowledge Policies Group) dell'IGSG (Istituto di Informatica Giuridica e Sistemi Giudiziari)/CNR (Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche)

Poland: [CENTRUM CYFROWE](#)

Spain: [FESABID](#)

The project explores these issues to lay the groundwork for identifying the key challenges and potential benefits behind (i)SDL implementation. The project outcomes could provide a foundation for future strategies to overcome these obstacles and support the mission of libraries in the digital realm.

⁸ E-lending in the (i)SDL model was developed as part of the report *eBooks and Secure Digital Lending in European Libraries* (scheduled for publication in January/February 2025). In detail, e-lending based on the (i)SDL model is characterised by the following features: 1) Loans are made by strictly defined entities - establishments accessible to the public (e.g., libraries) that derive no direct or indirect economic or commercial advantage from their lending activity (requirement for a special case); 2) Lending covers the lending of a digital copy of a book; 3) Loans are made under the one copy - one user model; 4) Lending is carried out in a mimetic (i.e., allowing patrons to download electronic copies of books) or a quasi-mimetic fashion (i.e., allowing the use of electronic copies of books in streaming); 5) Lending is only for a limited period; 6) After the lending period has expired, the user cannot use the e-book; 7) A digital copy of a book must be obtained from a lawful source, but the library can make an electronic copy of a legally obtained copy of a paper book; e-lending under the (i)SDL model gives rise to the right to remuneration (PLR) in line with the Rental and Lending Directive; 8) there is no transfer of data, including personal data of library patrons, to publishers or other third parties.

The questionnaire is divided into eight sections and contains **36 questions**.

Given the topic's relevance, please take about **20 minutes** to respond to the questionnaire we have prepared.

The deadline for completing the questionnaire is **February 26th, 2025**.

We greatly appreciate your participation in this survey, as your responses will directly contribute to shaping the future of (i)SDL in libraries across Europe.

I. LIBRARY'S PROFILE

1. For which library are you responding to this questionnaire? (Add the library's name)

Indicate the ISIL code (in the ICCU registry) of your library

2. What is your role in the library?

3. What type of library are you answering for? Following [IFLA's typology](#):

- National
- Academic
- Public
- School
- Other ù

4. What types of collections does your library primarily hold?
(Select all that apply)

- Serials (e.g., journals, magazines, periodicals)
- Monographs (e.g., books, reports)
- Archival materials (e.g., manuscripts, historical documents)
- Multimedia (e.g., DVDs, audio recordings, images)
- Digital-only resources (e.g., e-books, databases, online journals)
- Public domain or out-of-copyright materials
- Other (please specify) _____

5. What is the size of your library's physical collection?

- Small (less than 1,000 records)
- Medium (1,000–10,000 records)
- Large (10,000–50,000 records)
- Very large (Over 50,000 records)

6. What is the size of your library's digital collection?

- Small (less than 1,000 records)
- Medium (1,000–10,000 records)
- Large (10,000–50,000 records)
- Very large (Over 50,000 records)

7. Does your library have a dedicated team to manage digital services or collections?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

II. DIGITAL LENDING

8. Does your library provide an e-lending service?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

9. If you answer "yes" to the question above, please specify your library's current digital lending model.

- Digital lending provided for specific resources
- Digital lending fully provided
- I don't know

10. Does your library digitise physical works and lend digital copies under (i)SDL?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

11. If you answer "yes" to the question above, which of the following types of material do you lend under (i)SDL?

(Select all that apply)

- Public domain works
- In-copyright works which are out of commerce
- In-copyright works which are on sale but only in paper format
- In-copyright works which are on sale, also in electronic format
- Other (please specify) _____
- I don't know

12. Is there/would there be a demand for (i)SDL services from your library's users?

- Yes, there is high demand

- Yes, but the demand is moderate
- Very little demand
- No demand
- I don't know

Please specify your answer

13. Do you foresee that this demand, in the coming years, will:

- Increase strongly
- Increase marginally
- Stay stable
- Decline
- I don't know

14. In your opinion, how important is it for your library to offer a (i)SDL service?

- Essential
- Important but not essential
- Not important
- I don't know

Please explain why:

III. LEGAL BARRIERS

15. Does your national copyright law or other legislation authorise (i)SDL, and under what conditions?

16. How clear is your country's national copyright law or other legislation regarding (i)SDL?

- Very clear
- Somewhat clear
- Not clear at all
- I don't know

IV. TECHNOLOGICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE BARRIERS

17. What technological barriers has your library encountered – or might encounter – in implementing (i)SDL?

(Please rate each barrier on a scale from 0 to 5, where 0=I don't know, 1 = Not a barrier and 5 = Major barrier)

Barrier	0=I don't know	1 (Not a barrier)	2	3	4	5 (Major barrier)
Lack of adequate digitisation equipment	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Lack of an adequate archiving system	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Inadequate digital rights management (DRM) system or lack of technical protection measures know-how	<input type="checkbox"/>					

If you think there are other technological barriers, please indicate them below:

18. Is your library part of a consortium or collaboration that could share technological resources or infrastructures to enable (i)SDL?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

If you answered Yes, please specify which consortium or collaboration

V. RISK OF OPPOSITION

19. Do you face resistance from within your institution (e.g., staff or administration) to implementing (i)SDL?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

If you answered "Yes" to the previous question, please specify

20. In your opinion, are libraries in your country reluctant to implement (i)SDL because of concerns about potential legal actions from publishers or authors?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- Other (please specify)_____

21. In your opinion, are libraries in your country reluctant to implement (i)SDL because of concerns about potential technological barriers?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- Other (please specify) _____

22. How would the publishing industry in your country respond to the idea of (i)SDL?

- Strongly supportive
- Neutral
- Opposed
- I don't know

VI. HUMAN RESOURCES

23. Does your library have access to legal expertise to address copyright and (i)SDL-related issues?

- Yes, we have dedicated legal staff or advisor
- No, we lack the necessary legal support
- Other (please specify) _____
- I don't know

24. Has your library staff received training or guidance on (i)SDL's legal aspects?

- Yes, extensive training
- Yes, but limited training
- No training has been provided
- In progress
- I don't know

If you answer "No" or "In progress" to the question above, please explain any challenges related to human resources:

25. Do you think such legal training or guidance is necessary?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

26. Does your library have access to technological expertise to address (i)SDL-related issues?

- Yes, we have dedicated staff or advisor
- No, we lack the necessary technological support
- Other (please specify) _____
- I don't know

27. Has your library staff received training or guidance on (i)SDL's technological aspects (e.g., digital rights management, archiving systems, etc.)?

- Yes, extensive training
- Yes, but limited training
- No training has been provided
- In progress
- I don't know

If you answer “No” or “In progress” to the question above, please explain any challenges related to human resources:

28. Do you think such technological training or guidance is necessary?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

VII. FINANCIAL BARRIERS

29. Does your library have adequate financial resources to implement (i)SDL?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

30. Are digitisation tools and DRM systems affordable for the library?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

VIII. OTHER

31. Would you or your staff benefit from more information/formative events on (i)SDL?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

32. In your opinion, what steps should national policymakers take to facilitate (i)SDL adoption in libraries?

33. Do you think (i)SDL will become more relevant for libraries in the future?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Please specify why

34. Could the library's (i)SDL system integrate with existing catalogues and platforms?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

35. Can the library secure users' personal and digital content data by providing (i)SDL?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

36. What are the negative consequences of not providing (i)SDL?

(Select all that apply)

- The library loses its relationship with users
- The library cannot allow a user to read a book if he/she cannot go to the library personally and the publisher has not provided an e-book version of the book.
- Users are less likely to engage with the library's services
- The library may face increased pressure to offer digital access options
- The library's services become less competitive than other libraries or digital platforms.
- There are none
- Other (please specify) _____
- I don't know

Appendix B - Excerpt of the most significant free-text comments

1. Comment to question n. 12 "Is there/would there be a demand for (i)SDL services from your library's users?": Most readers prefer printed books.
2. Comment to question n. 14 "In your opinion, how important is it for your library to offer a (i)SDL service?": [The (i)SDL] At the moment, it is not a priority based on user demand. However, it could become an interesting project in the future for specific collections.
3. Comment to question n. 14 "In your opinion, how important is it for your library to offer a (i)SDL service?": The average age of loyal users is medium to high, and they are still not very interested in digital formats.
4. Comment to question n. 27 "Has your library staff received training or guidance on (i)SDL's technological?": Lack of staff dedicated to digitization.

5. Comment to question n. 27 “Has your library staff received training or guidance on (i)SDL’s technological”: Lack of staff training.

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⁹ <https://www.aib.it/>